

THE TEACHING PROFESSION, ITS EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article discusses the pedagogical profession, its emergence and development.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, journalism, development, psychology, speech and writing*

ПРОФЕССИЯ УЧИТЕЛЯ, ЕЁ СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается педагогическая профессия, её становление и развитие.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогика, журналистика, развитие, психология, речь и письмо.*

The formation of the pedagogical profession is inextricably linked with the history of human development. Primitive people, who lived by gathering food, took children with them and taught them to hunt, pick fruits of various trees, dig up the roots of plants, and search for water sources. Such actions were carried out by experienced people of the tribe (tribe) or elders. Based on the actions taken to meet ordinary daily needs, they gave young people information based on existing experiences and formed practical skills in them. Children learned to warn others of approaching danger by making various sounds based on the examples of adults.

Before the emergence of speech and writing, such actions were carried out on the basis of gestures. The emergence of speech and writing, which made a fundamental revolution in human history, as well as the division of labor activities performed by the collective into various areas, allowed the attitude towards young people to acquire a progressive character. The natural need to protect themselves from the effects of various natural disasters, treat diseases that threaten people's lives, and accumulate enough food for survival showed that it was advisable to give young people life experiences by people who had sufficient knowledge in a certain field of labor activity. As a result, a group of people was formed who taught children life experiences, and special places began to be organized to provide children with knowledge in certain areas.

The first schools appeared in the ancient East (Babylon, Egypt, India), where children were taught the basics of administrative and economic management. In ancient times, schools functioned as an important component of the educational system of Sparta, Athens, and Rome. In ancient Greece, such places were called academies. The word "academy" comes from the name of the legendary hero Academia. In the 4th century BC, Plato lectured to his students in a place called Academia near Athens, and later the educational institution began to be called by that name. In ancient Rome and Greece, philosophers were responsible for educating children. As a result of the stratification of society, slaves were responsible for transporting children to and from educational institutions in the feudal system, and they were called "pedagogues." The meaning of this concept is "child-leader". In the later stages of historical development, people who were constantly involved in giving children systematic knowledge began to be called by this name. During feudalism, most schools were organized under mosques (in Muslim countries) or temples (India).

In such schools, young people were taught secular knowledge along with religious knowledge. During the Middle Ages, educational institutions in the form of academies also operated in the East, which were called "House of the Wise" (9th century, Bao'dod), "Academy of Mamun" (early 11th century, Khorezm), and societies under observatories (15th century, Samarkand). Encyclopedic scientists with strong knowledge in various fields of science were attracted to the academies, and they conducted extensive research in such areas as mathematics, geodesy, mineralogy, medicine, and astronomy. In the Middle Ages and in societies based on capital production, special importance was attached to the work of spiritually and morally mature teachers with excellent knowledge in various fields in schools in the form of academies (madrasas in the East).

For example, in the madrasas founded by Muhammad Tarao'ay Ulu'bek, famous scholars of their time - Ali Kushchi, Taftazani, Qazizoda Rumi, Mavlano Muhammad, O'iyasiddin Jamshid Koshiy, Muiniddin Koshiy and Mansur Koshiy taught students. The founders of the Jadidism movement that emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, famous enlighteners - Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy, Munavvar Qori, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoz, Abdulla Avloniy, Abdukadir Shakuriy, Ismatulla Rakhmatullaev, Abdurauf Fitrat, Isohkhon Ibrat and others became famous among the population not only as mentors, but also as spiritually mature people.

2. Eastern thinkers and Western educators about the role of the teaching profession in society. The demands placed on the teacher by society were reflected in the works of Eastern thinkers and Western enlighteners of their time. Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi and Abu Rayhan al-Biruni attached particular importance to the spiritual and moral maturity of the teacher. In their opinion, a good teacher differs from others in one aspect, namely, he willingly teaches the knowledge he has to young people and can be an example for them in every matter.

Abu Ali ibn Sina, emphasizing in his works the need for a teacher to fulfill the responsible duty of educating children, gives them the following recommendations that are a guarantee of success in their activities:

- 1) be calm and serious in dealing with children;
- 2) pay attention to the assimilation of the knowledge being given by students; 3) use of various forms and methods in education;
- 4) knowledge of the student's memory, ability to acquire knowledge, personal characteristics; 5) interest in science;
- 6) ability to distinguish the most important of the knowledge being given;
- 7) provide knowledge to students in a way that is understandable and appropriate to their age and mental level;
- 8) ensure that each word is at a level that arouses the child's emotions¹.

Alisher Navoi, condemning the qualities possessed by some schoolmasters of his time, in particular, harshness, greed and ignorance, sets serious requirements for the spiritual image of a teacher. In particular, "a teacher should not be a man of honor and not try to teach knowledge that he does not know, not be eager to teach for the sake of pride and not talk and joke for the sake of arrogance, not wear a big turban and a long skirt because of ignorance, and not have a place for him on the madrasah porch for gossip. ... If he fears evil and avoids impurity, not only does he not think that he is a scholar and allows various immoral acts to many ignorant people,

but also makes it lawful for him to do things that he should not do, and if it becomes a rule for him not to do things that he should do. This is not a teacher, he is a spreader of bad habits”

At the same time, he emphasizes the hard work of the teacher: “His work is beyond the power of man, not a man, but even a giant cannot do it. A strong man would be powerless to protect one young child, but he teaches a bunch of children knowledge and manners, what can a handsome man do to that. There is also the fact that there are few people in that bunch who have understanding, how can such a person be subjected to hundreds of hardships. No matter what, young children have a lot of rights. Even if a student reaches the throne, it is worth serving him (the teacher). With the regret of who taught you a single letter in the path of truth, the famous pedagogue Abdulla Avloni also gives a special place to expressing views on the personality of the teacher and his activities in his works. The scholar notes that while parents play a special role in the healthy growth of a child, the role of the teacher in his intellectual development is incomparable. In particular, he emphasizes that the formation of children's intellectual abilities is "a sacred task that rests on the attention and conscience of teachers," and says that "the power, beauty, breadth of thought are due to the upbringing of the teacher."2 In his time, Jan Amos Comenius highly appreciated the role of the teacher in developing the child's worldview, emphasizing that teaching is "a very honorable profession that stands higher than any other profession on earth." In the author's opinion, a teacher must be able to deeply understand his duties and fully appreciate his own worth.

Ya.A. Komensky, describing the image of a teacher, emphasizes the appropriateness of the manifestation of the following qualities in his personality: conscientious, hardworking, persistent, moral, loving his work, treating students like fathers, instilling in them a desire for knowledge, leading students to follow him, and religious faith. K.D. Ushinsky highly appreciates the spirituality and professional activity of teachers and puts forward the idea that it is appropriate to constantly improve their professional qualifications. For the first time, he substantiates the system that confirms the social significance of this idea - the system of training teachers.

It is appropriate for a student to pay attention to the clear and complete expression of his opinion in the process of communication with parents and colleagues. In the process of communicating with them, it is not enough to bring evidence of negative situations, but, on the contrary, to acknowledge the successes of the student (or colleague, parents), to express confidence in their further enrichment, which allows them to communicate with him. During the communication process, the teacher's words should convey goodwill, sincerity, and a friendly attitude towards the interlocutor, as well as be in the best possible mood. As an active participant in the process of pedagogical communication, the teacher must achieve a number of qualities in himself.

First of all, he must be thoughtful, calm, able to correctly assess the situation, and be able to resolve existing conflicts. It is advisable for the student to pay attention to the clear and complete expression of his opinion in the process of communication with parents and colleagues. In the process of communicating with them, it is necessary not to bring evidence of negative situations, but, on the contrary, to acknowledge the successes of the student (or colleague, parents), to express confidence in their further enrichment, which will allow them to

communicate with him. In the process of communication, it is necessary that the teacher's words convey goodwill, sincerity, and friendliness towards the interlocutor, as well as to be in the best possible mood. The image of the teacher's personality that meets these requirements ensures his respect and admiration among students, colleagues, and parents.

References

1. Pedagogika fanining paydo bo'lishi hamda pedagogika fanining ob'ekti, predmeti, maqsad va vazifalarini o'rganish va konspekt qilish (Pedagogika // M.X.Toxataxodjaeva umumiy tahriri ostida. – T.: Faylasuflar Milliy jamiyati, 2010. –b. 28-31; Ibragimov X., Abdullaeva SH. Pedagogika nazariyasi. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya” nashriyoti, 2008. – b.26-28; PodlasyyI.P. Pedagogika – M: Vysshееobrazovanie, 2008. – S.39-50).
2. Pedagogikaning asosiy kategoriyalarini o'rganish, tahlil etish va jadval ko'rinishida daftarga qayd etish (Pedagogika // M.X.Toxataxodjaeva umumiy tahriri ostida. – T.: Faylasuflar Milliy jamiyati, 2010. –b. 31-32; Ibragimov X., Abdullaeva SH. Pedagogika nazariyasi. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya” nashriyoti, 2008. –b.29-31; PodlasyyI.P. Pedagogika – M: Vysshееobrazovanie, 2008. – S.51-61.).
3. Jeff Halstead. Navigating the new pedagogy. R and Education, 2011.